

THE AIRSTICKS: A NEW INTERFACE FOR ELECTRONIC PERCUSSIONISTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper documents the early developments of a new interface for electronic percussionists. The interface is designed to allow the composition, improvisation and performance of live percussive electronic music using hand, finger, foot and head movements captured by various controllers. This paper provides a background to the field of electronic percussion, outlines the artistic motivations behind the project, and describes the technical nature of the work completed so far. This includes the development of software, the combination of existing controllers and senses, and an example mapping of movement to sound.

1. INTRODUCTION

The work presented in this paper is motivated by a desire to give percussionists control over complex sound textures at the same time as allowing them to time and execute precise rhythmic gestures. Such an interface takes advantage of the motor skills of an expert percussionist and combines it with all the real-time control over sound permitted by modern software.

In previous work, we developed an interface that allowed percussionists to manipulate sounds using head movements in a manner that did not interfere with the traditional four-limbed playing of their instrument. However, since then, we have shifted our focus to deconstructing the traditional approach to triggering sounds - namely, by striking a drum skin or a pad - and replacing it with sounds triggered by striking the air, allowing the performer to have more control over the sound both before and after the sound is triggered.

This paper will provide a brief background to the development of electronic percussion instruments, from the earliest electronic pads to the creation of gestural sensors, particularly the Radio Baton [1] [2]. The authors' own gestural interface, called the AirSticks, will be discussed, including a brief overview of the development of the de-

sign, how the design criteria has changed over the course of the instruments development and future plans for development and assessment.

1.1 Gestural Controllers

Gestural controllers, or 'open-air' controllers as they are referred to by Rovin and Hayward [3], allow tremendous freedom for sonic control. Such interfaces 'unchain the performer from the physical constraints of holding, touching, and manipulating an instrument' [3]. However, by their nature, they can weaken the perceptual relationship between gestures and sonic output. The relatively unlimited range of possible mappings of gesture to sound requires a performer to devote much time to learning different mapping scenarios and develop a routine of practicing to relate movements to change in sound [4]. This has given rise to much literature concerning the most effective design and pedagogical factors in designing novel instruments. See these papers for a rigorous treatment of these factors [5] [6].

The decoupling of physical contact with sonic output causes another perceptual issue relating to the feedback channel that helps performers regulate timing. It is well-established that accurate, repeatable and timely feedback -- whether it be physical or acoustic -- is required for a performer to comfortably deliver expressive performance [7] [8] [9] [10].

The technical innovation behind the development of the AirSticks is designed to take full advantage of the performance possibilities that open up when a percussionist is not required to strike a surface, but the speed and accuracy of the method for sensing when a strike occurs allows the perceptual feedback to be closed in a comfortable and satisfying way.

Position and rotation data for two 'sticks' is captured and analysed by a custom piece of software running on OSX which outputs MIDI data. This data is accompanied by MIDI data containing information about hand, finger, foot and head movements. Combined, these data provide the performer and composer with a plethora of mapping possibilities.

Mulder suggests that new musical instruments should be designed around the existing motor skills that a performer may already possess [11]. The AirSticks opens the door

to creating a novel instrument that allows performers to utilise the hours of practice that traditional drum kit players have already dedicated, building on their existing technique in new ways to create an instrument that is both intimate for the performer [12] and transparent for the audience [13] [14]. The AirSticks also focus on maintaining the relationship between energy put in and the sonic output [15]. In other words, the AirSticks is an electronic drum kit that builds on traditional drum practice, celebrates advances in technology, is electronic in nature yet maintains a physically plausible relationship between movement and sound.

2. BACKGROUND

The term electronic percussion in this paper refers to instruments which are played like traditional acoustic percussive instruments, but instead have an electronic output. It could be argued that since the invention of the microphone, all acoustic percussion instruments in the studio and in bigger live contexts have had an electronic output which has led to the ability to manipulate each individual sound. Modern top-of-the-range electronic drum kits market themselves on giving the performer ultimate control over the drum samples they trigger, by allowing the editing of parameters such of virtual microphone placement, room size, drum skin tension, drum size and drum material. This culture of attempting to emulate acoustic drum kits with electronic percussion is not of interest to us, rather, we seek to build on the tradition of triggering sounds that an acoustic drum kit cannot produce, sounds that reflect the culture of the modern electronic producer. However, we also aim to incorporate the control of all four limbs gained by acoustic drummers into this completely different sounding instrument.

2.1 Early Electronic Pads

The earliest example of an electronic pad is Leon Theremin's Keyboard Electronic Timpani designed in 1932 though it wasn't until the 1960s and the invention of modular synthesis that electronic pads became more common place [16]. A particularly celebrated example of this is Schneider and Hutter's Electronic Percussion Musical Instrument, patented in 1977 and used in the seminal electronic band Kraftwerk [17]. It is a device made up of metallic pads and metal sticks connected to the pads with an electric chord. Upon striking the pad, the percussionist completes a circuit of white noise or a sinusoidal wave for the short time that the stick and pad are in contact, similar to plugging a lead into a modular synthesizer and quickly pulling it out. This simple device is a good example of merging physical movement with electronic sound in a new way.

2.2 The Electronic Drum Pad

In more recent years, with the increase in speed of computers and the introduction of MIDI, electronic pads have been used to trigger samples as opposed to closing circuits. This has meant that any sound can be assigned to a strike of the electronic pad. Though there has been many

recent advances in this technology, very little information other than velocity and the precise location of the strike on the surface can be captured [18].

2.3 The Radio Baton

Some musicians have decided that more information needs to be captured by the computer to enable the creation of electronic percussive instruments that may be as expressive as acoustic ones. One example of this is the Radio Baton, a gesture sensor that allows the tracking of a mallet-like stick in three dimensional space [2]. Instead of sending a trigger over MIDI on impact, this instrument sends a MIDI note-on message when the mallet crosses an invisible plane above an antenna board. Boulanger calls this plane the hit-level [2]. A second plane, called the set-level, is positioned just above the hit-level. This plane acts as a note-off trigger to avoid double-triggering. As well as generating note-on triggers this instrument also captures and sends XYZ position data. Schloss uses all this data to allow three levels of control: a timbral level, a note level and the control of a musical process [1]. It is this control of a musical process that gives the electronic percussionist greater control over musical expression than can be gained from a two dimensional surface. Since the computer is constantly receiving XYZ position data, control changes can be made before and after a strike, giving the performer of the Radio Baton extra control and expressivity.

3. CAPTURING MOVEMENT

The AirSticks uses a similar principle to the Radio Baton in capturing both trigger commands and XYZ data¹. The primary difference is that instead of using invisible planes, the AirSticks uses rotation around the X-axis to send note-on and note-off information. This change brings the triggering gesture far more in line with the actual performance of a drummer [19] [20]. In this section we will describe the evolution of this project and why we came to our particular conclusions.

3.1 Project History

We would like to note that so far in this project we have not developed a formal experimental framework. Instead we have decided to develop the new instrument over the past ten years through Ilisar's creative practice as a full time drummer and performer. Before meeting Havryliv, Ilisar pursued new ways of playing electro-acoustic percussion. He designed what he called the EAPP (electro-acoustic percussive pads) which featured an array of small junk percussion bits attached to a Perspex drum, with Piezo transducers glued to each item. The idea was that these sounds, since they were all acoustic in nature as opposed to being samples from a computer, would give the percussionist an experience more related to that of playing an acoustic instrument, yet still enable the manipulation of the sounds using audio effects. At first, Ilisar used a Kaoss Pad, an effect unit that allows the user to

¹ Where the X axis parallel to the ground running across the performer

change different parameters of the effect using a touch pad. Ilsar performed gigs playing miked up hi-hats and bass drum with his feet, the EAPP with one hand and the Kaoss Pad with the other. This obviously impeded his ability to play more complicated cross-rhythms.

Around the same time Havryliv designed a jacket he used to manipulate other performers in his own live performance situations [21]. The jacket used mercury tilt sensors that enabled a performer, with the movement of their arms, to change the parameters of a Pure-Data patch as audio went into his computer. Havryliv designed a similar wearable item for Ilsar, in the form of a hat. Ilsar replaced his Kaoss Pad with his hat, and could now perform with all four limbs and manipulate sounds by tilting his head. He went on to perform with this set up at the Great Escape Festival with Comatone and Foley, and at the Sydney Opera House with Gauche. For those acts, Ilsar mapped sampled sounds from these bands' respective albums to the Roland SPD20 electronic multi-pad and Roland KD7 foot triggers.

We then pursued designing a new open-air controller system where instead of triggering samples off a laptop by hitting a pad, samples could be triggered by striking the air. This led us to the three different technologies.

3.2 Infrared and Cameras

We experimented with infrared tracking by placing four infrared LED lights on the end of a mallet forming a square shape. This is based on technology developed by Kim [22]. An infrared camera connected to the computer would then track these four lights, and according to the size and shape created, information would be sent to another software to provide the XYZ position and limited rotation data. This solution had its problems:

- A suitable lighting environment may not always be available, a device that could be used in the standard club, pub or concert hall was desired.
- The tracking of two of these mallets at the same time could cause serious interference to the data.
- Though the latency was relatively low (10msec), it was not low enough to enable the percussionist to feel like they could be confident that a sound would be triggered at the precise moment they expect.

3.3 Exoskeleton

The idea with an exoskeleton was that all the different rotation of joints from the shoulder, elbow and wrist, would result in the location of the sticks held by the percussionist [23]. After attempting to build an exoskeleton, we decided to trial the Gypsy 6 Suit. Problems with this interface were:

- The six sensors on each arm did not give us an exact location of the hands.
- It was cumbersome to wear, restrictive to move in and easy to break.
- It needed calibrating before each performance.

3.4 Gaming Controllers

The Razer Hydra Gaming Controllers comprise of two joysticks tethered to a base station, which connects to a computer using USB (see Figure 1). The joysticks can be moved freely in space (so far as the tethering cables permit) and their position and orientation is determined by their relationship to a sphere on the base station, which uses some magnetic sensing system amongst other sensors. The device has a sampling rate of 250 Hz, with measurement precision to the millimeter and degree for position and orientation, respectively. These controllers are cheap and an open source gaming community has already developed online with members releasing MIDI software which the authors began to experiment with. These controllers also come with an SDK, a set of C++ APIs which allow the developer to read the state of the motion controllers. The state comprises position and orientation (6-DOF), and the button states. An OSX application was developed based on this SDK which translates the user's movements to a graphical representation (see Figure 2). Other advantages such as weight, ease of set up, low-to-no interference and extra buttons for control meant the authors could commit to designing a new triggering system with these controllers.

4. THE AIRSTICKS

At first, we attempted to take the information of velocity and acceleration to decipher what the performer meant as a strike. Trigger detection was based on detecting spikes in acceleration and jerk (the time derivative of acceleration). This method was inspired by the performance gesture associated with a real drum kit: a stick would be moving downward at a reasonably constant velocity, would hit the drum skin and experience a large change in velocity which is detected as a peak in acceleration. The velocity and acceleration derivatives are constantly calculated from the position data sent from the device, and when an acceleration value that exceeds a particular threshold is recorded, a trigger was detected.

Figure 1. The Razer Hydra Gaming Controllers [24].

This approach suffered from two issues. Firstly, in the absence of a surface to impact with, the performer would naturally slow down their motion just prior to triggering -

this diminished the magnitude of potential acceleration peaks. Secondly, setting a constant threshold for trigger detection from acceleration data made it difficult to detect triggers across the range of potential gestures. In lowering the threshold intentional smaller movements would warrant a strike, but unintended jitters and shocks would also trigger a sound.

A machine learning method based on Neural Networks was developed that analysed velocity data alongside acceleration data. Upon recognising a peak in acceleration data, the velocity gesture leading up to that peak was analysed to see if it matched the velocity profile of a large range of strikes that had been recorded and learned in the past. This improved the performance of the trigger-detection, but even minor inconsistencies made it a frustrating and uncomfortable experience for the performer trying to accurately control musical performance timings.

4.1 Triggering System

The breakthrough occurred when we realized that instead of training the technology to enable the instrument to learn what the performer’s intentions are, the performer should learn how to play a consistent non-complicated instrument. This is in line with the literature on imaginary design and mappings. We devised a system of imaginary planes, similar to that of the Radio Baton, but instead of having a hit-level and a set-level, the rotation data sent from the gaming controllers is used. When the performer’s wrist passed through a particular angle of rotation around the X axis, resembling the movement of a strike, a note-on would be triggered. The XYZ position data would determine the note-on number, splitting the 3D space into a 4x2x2 grid (see Figure 2). The performer quickly found consistency in finding this trigger angle, and could even anticipate it. An auditory response in this new instrument had replaced the tactile one of the electronic pads.

Figure 2. The AirSticks’ Graphic User Interface.

This also allowed us to permit striking up and down through a point to improve the speed at which the instrument could be played. Velocity of the strike could still be interpreted, as the speed at which the controller passes through this point was also captured and sent to the computer. The angle of trigger was set to different degrees

depending on the height of the strike. A strike high up would use a trigger angle of close to 90 degrees, or perpendicular to the ground, whereas the lowest angle trigger points would be set to 0 degrees, or parallel to the ground, with all other trigger angles in between being scaled appropriately, as if the performer was playing an invisible concave plane (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. The threshold of the trigger angle against the distance from the bottom of the virtual space.

4.2 Thumb, Finger, Foot and Head Movements

Having created a consistent system for capturing the performer’s movements using the Razer Hydra Gaming Controllers, we embarked on capturing other movements by the percussionist, particular those that would not take away from being able to play the AirSticks with the hands. Like all modern gaming controllers, the Razer Hydras consist of a thumb joystick, a trigger button controlled with the index fingers, and several buttons on each hand. This gives the performer the ability to send information to the computer with more subtle gestures, movements that either need to be more easily made than large ones, or ones that the performer decides should be hidden from the audience. Foot movements are captured using the SoftStep Foot MIDI Controller (see Figure 4) which enables the performer to trigger up to ten sounds with the back of the toe or heel or make up over forty more controller changes. Finally, head movements are captured using an accelerometer placed on top of the performer’s head that acts as a tilt sensor.

4.3 Graphic User Interface

The gaming controllers interface to an application designed for Mac OSX built on the Razer Hydra SDK, which provides a user interface for using the controllers and which outputs MIDI data based on position/orientation and gesture analysis (continuous and discrete, respectively). This arrangement provides the highest possible sampling rate and fidelity from the device, which in turn permits the use of sophisticated engineering techniques to analyse motion, and provide performance-time gestural analysis and response. A predictive filtering scheme based on Kalman state estimation is used to ef-

fectively up-sample the gestural analysis system to 1kHz, well beyond the perceptual limit for the sensation of causal association between gesture and aural result [25].

Figure 4. Keith McMillen’s SoftStep Foot Controller [26].

The Graphic User Interface or GUI, is made of a grid and two floating points that represent the middle of each controller. This enables a simple visual representation of the virtual space. The performer can see in which grid each hand is in, and note that when they tilt past the trigger angle, the grid lights up, signaling a note-on message. The GUI also provides a MIDI trainer, a function extremely useful when using programs such as Ableton Live for the sound mapping. The MIDI trainer function enables a simple way to map control changes in the GUI to ones in Ableton Live. Another way of mapping sounds and control changes is by noting which numbers they are being sent on. This facilitates an easy way of sending MIDI to all sorts of other instruments and programs.

4.4 Mapping

Currently, all information from all sensors makes its way into Ableton Live 9. Here a world of possible mappings exists. We will now outline an example of one of the mappings of movement to sound we have made for the AirSticks, tying in to Schnell and Battier’s concept of a ‘composed instrument’ [27]. We will focus on the way the gestures correspond to sound triggering and manipulation and avoid much of the technical work.

4.4.1 The AirSticks 16 Drum Rack

This mapping is the most developed to date and aims to allow the performer as much choice for solo or group improvisation as possible, while maintaining intimacy and transparency, keeping with the literature. The AirSticks 16 Drum Rack mapping utilises the 4x4x2 grid (see Figure 1) to allow the performer to trigger any of sixteen sounds in a virtual space around them. The GUI is compatible with Ableton Live’s Drum Rack virtual instrument which also defaults to a sixteen sample array. The mapping allocates a group of samples for each box of the grid and foot triggers, and makes it possible to switch through different sounds using various buttons on the controllers. Rotating past a predetermined point on the X rotation triggers the sound that corresponds to the box the AirStick is in, mimicking a percussive strike. The velocity is determined by the speed at which this rotation is made and is mapped to volume and brightness. Aside from Note On and Off messages, control change information correlating to finger, thumb, hand, foot and head

movements also makes its way into Ableton Live through the GUI. There are a large number of modes of effects that can be called up using the buttons on the controllers. Different modes basically switch on different effects, whose parameters are mapped to some of the below in Table 1.

Movement	Parameter(s)
LPosX	Reverb Input Filter Frequency
LPosY	Reverb Input Filter Width; Noise Gain Left
LPosZ	All Effects Gains
LRotX	Chorus Delay 1 Time; Grain Delay Pitch; Fragulator Playback Speed; Ping Pong Delay Time Delay
LRotY	Chorus Delay 1 High Pass Frequency; Grain Delay Frequency; High Pass Filter Frequency
LRotZ	Panning Of Respective Effect
LJoyX	Fragulator Amp Variation; Ping Pong Delay Filter Frequency
LJoyZ	Chorus LFO Amount; Reverb Decay Time; Grain Delay Feedback; Fragulator Repetition; Noise Centre Frequency Left; Ping Pong Delay Filter Width
LTrig	Sends into Same Respective Returns
RPosX	Reverb Early Reflections Spin Rate
RPosY	Reverb Early Reflections Spin Amount; Noise Gain Right; Noise Track Volume
RPosZ	Pitch
RRotX	Chorus Delay 2 Delay Time; Grain Delay Random Pitch
RRotY	Low Pass Filter Frequency
RRotZ	Panning Of Respective Effect
RJoyX	Chorus LFO Rate
RJoyZ	Chorus LFO Amount; Reverb Decay Time; Grain Delay Spray; Grain Delay Time Delay; Noise Centre Frequency Right
RTrig	Microphone Audio Track Sends to Respective Returns
HeadX	Master Panning
HeadZ	Master Volume

Table 1. Mapping of movement² to sound.

In general, movements to the right and down result in lower pitch manipulation, while movements upwards and towards the audience result in an increase in intensity. Of particular interest with this mapping is the use of the right trigger button, controlled by the movement of the index figure, to turn the gain up of a microphone placed near the performer, and the use of the left trigger button to turn

² L – Left; R – Right; Pos – Position; Rot – Rotation; Joy – Joystick; Trig – Trigger.

up an internal feedback loop. This allows the performer to ‘tune’ the room, using the acoustics of the room to create feedback tones and drones. It is our intention to develop this approach further as it brings an electro-acoustic element to a purely electronic instrument. It also means that if the performer does not react to the feedback created by their movements they can lose control of the sound. This creates a greater dialogue between the instrument and performer. It also allows the performer to manipulate other sounds in their environment, whether it be their voice, other musicians, the audience, or the surrounding sounds. To best understand this mapping there is a demonstration at

www.alonilsar.com/composer/airsticks

5. FUTURE RESEARCH

We are interested in not only using the current set up of the AirSticks in a variety of ways, but also continually changing aspects of the instrument to suit different pieces of work. Other mappings for the AirSticks that have been conceived are listed here below. All of these attempt to maintain the relationship between physical energy input and sound output.

- *FerguCircles* – designed to allow the performer to play samples using granular synthesis by forming circles with their hands around any of the three planes.
- *Bouncy Balls* – an experiment with physical modeling and perpetual motion.
- *Synthesiser n* – designed to allow the performer to play melodies on any soft synth across a number of virtual boxes.
- *Spinning Plates* – designed for a piece of virtual spinning plates which each make different changing pitches.

Other uses and ideas for the AirSticks include:

- Working with sound convolution.
- Performing with other traditional and non-traditional instruments.
- Using the AirSticks in children’s theatre.
- Working with visual artists in creating a new Graphic User Interface that may be projected during performances.
- Establishing a set of rudiments to best practice and learn the instrument.
- Continually looking for new hardware devices that could potentially work even better with the GUI.

We will also soon invite other percussionists to play the instrument and get their feedback. We feel this is invaluable

to create a more intimate instrument. We have also already begun to put on performances using the AirSticks and asking for feedback from the audience in order to improve its transparency. We have also been gathering data on how musicians have reacted to playing in an ensemble that contains the AirSticks.

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